

1 **Sphk1 induction in active Crohn's Disease.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the blood in a cohort of 67 humans with the inflammatory bowel
7 disease (IBD) Crohn's Disease to discover genes associated with active disease in humans with CD. We
8 report here activation of Sphk1 in the hematopoietic compartment in humans with Crohn's Disease.

9 Citations

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